

AVIONICS FIBER-OPTIC AND PHOTONICS NETWORK PRELIMINARY TECHNOLOGY READINESS ASSESSMENT

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Abstract

Fiber-optic technology deployment on military platforms is driving the need to re-assess fiber optics and photonics technology readiness for next generation avionics systems. The AEROLAN initiative unveiled at the 22nd DASC and subsequently kicked off at the IEEE LEOS Avionics Fiber-Optics and Photonics workshop (AVFOP 2004), provides the impetus for a Technology Readiness Assessment (TRA) of the Naval aviation fiber-optics and photonics technology infrastructure.

TRA is a valuable methodology for defining technology maturity and making technology investment decisions. Technology Readiness Levels (TRLs) combined with Product Assessment Scales (PAs) are useful elements for assessing readiness prior to formulating research, development, and test and evaluation (RDT&E) objectives, and subsequent technology transition planning. This paper provides the reader insight into NAVAIR's preliminary readiness assessment of avionics fiber optics and photonics technology for the next generation.

Introduction

The IEEE and AIAA co-sponsored *Avionics Fiber-Optics and Photonics Technology Workshop (AVFOP 2004)* held in April, 2004 provided an overview status of avionics fiber-optics and photonics technology, and clarified a number of issues and concerns for the next generation of avionics fiber optic networks. *AVFOP 2004* resulted a number of takeaways and actions including the formulation of a new committee to develop the *AEROLAN* standard for next generation avionics fiber-optic networks [1]. The *AEROLAN* standardization work is ongoing and will be furthered at *AVFOP 2005*.

Technology Readiness Assessment (TRA) is a published methodology used by the Department of Defense (DoD) Science and Technology (S&T)

community to define the maturity (or readiness) of a given technology for potential use in DoD applications [2]. The DoD TRA process can be used by program managers as a recognized risk assessment tool before committing to transitioning new technology to a program or into the fleet. The TRA process can also be applied to the defense acquisition and engineering decision making process.

In this paper we have taken the results of *AVFOP 2004* as well as some recent NAVAIR fiber-optics and photonics technology development initiatives to give a "snapshot" preliminary readiness assessment of modern fiber-optics and photonics technology for potential application in next generation military avionics systems.

Technology Readiness Assessment

There are two methodologies for assessing technology readiness. The first is used extensively within the Department of Defense (DoD) and is defined in the *DoD Technology Readiness Assessment Deskbook*. Technology readiness level (TRL) scales of TRL 1 to TRL 9 are defined below whereby a score of TRL 1 indicates low maturity and a score of TRL 9 indicates high maturity:

TRL 1: Basic principals observed and reported.

TRL 2: Technology concept and/or application formulated.

TRL 3: Analytical and experimental critical function and/or characteristic proof of concept.

TRL 4: Component and/or breadboard validation in laboratory environment.

TRL 5: Component and/or breadboard validation in relevant environment.

TRL 6: System/subsystem model or prototype demonstration in a relevant environment.

TRL 7: System prototype demonstration in an operational environment.

TRL 8: Actual system completed and qualified through test and demonstration.

TRL 9: Actual system proven through successful mission operations.

The Integrated Microsystems Department at Sandia National Laboratory (Department of Energy) has published a Technology Readiness Level Product Assessment Scale (PA) that operates on a scale of 1 to 5 (PA1 to PA5) [3]. A score of PA1 indicates low maturity whereas a score of PA5 indicates high maturity. The PA scale definitions are as follows:

- PA 1: Research demonstration (Lab Demonstration).
- PA 2: Research prototype (Demonstration Unit).
- PA 3: Engineering prototype (Alpha Unit).
- PA 4: Flight / Field prototype (Beta Unit).
- PA 5: High Reliability (Production Unit).

Associating the TRL definitions with the PA definitions enables one to conclude:

- PA 1 encompasses TRL 1 to TRL 3.
- PA 2 encompasses TRL 4 to TRL 5.
- PA 3 encompasses TRL 6
- PA 4 encompasses TRL 7
- PA 5 encompasses TRL 8 to TRL 9.

NAVAIR Perspective

For decades NAVAIR has been instrumental in developing and transitioning fiber-optics and photonics technology to Naval aviation platforms. The AEROLAN standardization effort is one such example. AEROLAN is focusing on defining a standardized WDM backbone physical layer for the aerospace community, which can be truly protocol independent and scaleable in bandwidth, and still provide flexibility of architecture and growth potential. It is not at all obvious what the ideal AEROLAN WDM network node would consist of to implement the WDM backbone. It is the goal of this paper to give a preliminary assessment of existing technologies that could impact the

standardization decision-making process. In this paper we will attempt to skim the entire relevant fiber-optics and photonics technology landscape including network architecture, components and supportability.

Network Architectures

A variety of fiber-optic network architectures have been developed for use on aircraft. Here we define the TRL for each specific architecture category shown in Figure 1. To avoid misconceptions related to network qualification and maturity we are careful to define the type of aircraft (i.e., pressurized fuselage, tactical) to which the TRL is applicable. Please note these assessments are based on the authors' knowledge, and therefore should not be thought to be DoD-wide in their scope.

Figure 1. Network Architectures

Point-to-Point

Point-to-point link architectures have been the mainstay for aircraft communications for well over a decade. Based on its widespread use in a variety of aircraft types including pressurized fuselage aircraft and tactical aircraft, the point-to-point link is scored as TRL 9.

Bus

Bus architectures have been around for quite some time in the electronic/copper world and have seen fairly widespread application. Commercial examples include Ethernet for data networking and ARINC 429 for commercial aerospace.

Military applications include the omnipresent command and control bus, MIL-STD-1553. Although the optical bus equivalent based on AS1773 is well developed on paper, it has not seen widespread deployment on commercial or military aircraft. Therefore the bus architecture is scored TRL 7.

Switched Star

The switched star architecture resembles the layout of building wiring. A central node exists in the wiring closet and connections fan out to each one of the nodes, such as a telephone set or computer workstation. A commercial standard using both copper and optical media receiving widespread deployment is the Fibre Channel standard. On an aircraft, a central node contains the switch and connections fan out to the each of the avionics boxes or weapons replaceable assemblies (WRAs). A switched architecture based on optoelectronic switching is currently in Test & Evaluation on tactical aircraft. Full mission capability has not yet been completely proven. Therefore the switched star architecture is scored TRL 7.

Ring

The ring architecture (specifically, the dual counter rotating ring architecture) is the basis for the avionics LAN (AVLAN) on the Boeing 777 commercial jetliner. In the unlikely event that faults occur during flight, opto-mechanical bypass switching technology is used to reconfigure the

network. Based on the immense flight hour history and proven reliability of the AVLAN in the 777 fleet, the ring architecture is scored as TRL 9 for pressurized fuselage aircraft only. The application of ring architectures to the unpressurized environments of tactical aircraft has undergone much more limited evaluation. Consequently, its TRL is scored lower at TRL 5.

Mesh

The mesh architecture is one of the most complex architectures. It resembles the layout of the telecommunication grid. Each node (e.g. central office) is typically connected into the network via two or more paths. The multiple connections provide multiple paths to transfer information between point A and B. This capability allows the system to provide built in backup redundancy. It also can meet the needs of high peak demands by utilizing the redundant paths. Unfortunately, deterministic data transfer is difficult to guarantee and it is the most complicated to manage, especially since there is no central control node as in the switched star. In the commercial world, the mesh is TRL 9. The mesh has not been applied to any aerospace applications. However, discussions have begun around an *AEROLAN* standard, which could result in its application. Consequently, its TRL is still low, TRL 3.

Hybrid Variants

The emergence of waveguide optical amplifiers, photonic lightwave circuits (PLCs), and novel cable plants can enable the implementation of hybrid topologies which combine the best features of the above listed commercial network topologies to meet *AEROLAN* requirements. These options will be investigated under advanced architectural studies and modeling as part of the *AEROLAN* initiative.

Fiber-Optic Cable

Fiber-optic cable has been developed for use on a variety of commercial and military aircraft including the Boeing 777, Air Force F/A-22 Raptor, Air Force F-16 Fighting Falcon, Navy F/A-18 Hornet/Super Hornet, Air Force AWACS, Navy EP-3, Marines AV-8 Harrier, to name a few. To

date only multimode optical fiber has been deployed on a large scale. Two different cable designs have been used – loose tube construction and tight-buffered design. However, neither the loose tube nor tight-buffered designs have been qualified product listed (QPL'd). Large-scale deployment of single-mode fiber-optic cable has not yet been realized in the military/aerospace industry.

Based on its widespread use in a variety of aircraft types including pressurized fuselage aircraft and tactical aircraft, multimode fiber-optic cable is scored as TRL 8 to TRL 9. Figure 2 illustrates typical multimode fiber-optic cable construction. Single-mode fiber-optic cable is scored as TRL 6.

Figure 2. Fiber Optic Cable Design

Fiber-Optic Termini

MIL-PRF-29504

In the military-aerospace sector, the MIL-PRF-29504 /4 /5 fiber-optic ceramic terminus has been the *de facto* standard of the industry for multimode fiber-optic terminations (Figure 3 Style 1). Since this terminus has been qualified by the DoD and is on the Qualified Products List (QPL), the MIL-PRF-29504 ceramic terminus is scored as TRL 9.

The jeweled version of MIL-PRF-29504 /4 /5 terminus (Figure 3 Style 2) has also been a *de facto* standard for multimode fiber optic terminations on some platforms. However since the jeweled terminus has not been formally QPL'd, it is scored as TRL 7.

Figure 3. Fiber Optic Termini

1.25 mm Diameter Ferrules

New technology fiber optic termini based on the 1.25 mm outside diameter ceramic ferrule have been proposed for use in both military and commercial aircraft (Figure 4). The latest in terminus design features have been included in the most popular designs. ARINC has selected a terminus for use in pressurized fuselage commercial jetliner environments. The military has chosen a more rugged terminus design intended to survive the harsher Naval aviation platform environment.

Figure 4. New 1.25 mm Termini

The key benefit of these two new 1.25 mm diameter ferrule terminus designs is their ease of maintenance. The connectors housing the termini are hermaphroditic, and a removable alignment sleeve retainer exposes termini endfaces for ease of cleaning. Since these termini have not yet been QPL'd and in some cases are still untested, these termini are scored as TRL 3 to TRL 6 range.

Multifiber Array Ferrules

The commercial MT terminus has recently been proposed for use in avionics racks as part of a board-to-backplane connector. High temperature aerospace versions of the MT terminus would be highly desirable. Since the commercial MT terminus has not been QPL'd and has not been proven to be qualified for all relevant aircraft application environments, a TRL score of TRL 6 is given for the MT terminus.

Fiber-Optic Connectors

MIL-DTL-38999

The MIL-DTL-38999 connector has been the *defacto* standard workhorse connector for the military/aerospace industry (Figure 5). The fiber optic version of the MIL-DTL-38999 connector has been “qualified by similarity” on some military platforms. However, no formal qualification process or QPL-ing of fiber optic specific MIL-DTL-38999 connectors has been completed. Therefore the fiber optic version of the MIL-DTL-38999 connector is scored as TRL 7 to 8 depending on the actual connector configuration.

Figure 5. MIL-DTL-38999 Fiber Optic Connectors

Multimode Expanded Beam

Expanded beam connectors for 100/140 μm multimode fiber are deployed on Boeing 777 aircraft. Therefore expanded beam connectors are scored as TRL 9 for pressurized fuselage aircraft. Expanded beam connectors are being evaluated for tactical aircraft application. However, since none have gone into service yet, their TRL is scored 6.

Single-Mode Expanded Beam

Expanded beam connectors for single-mode fiber are currently under development and are in the test and evaluation community. Therefore, single-mode expanded beam connectors are scored as TRL 4-5.

Splices

Fiber optic mechanical splices exist in aircraft fiber optic support equipment maintenance kits for temporary repair of broken multimode fiber cable.

Both mechanical splicing for multimode fiber and fusion splicing for single-mode fiber are well developed in the commercial sector. However, no permanent multimode fiber optic mechanical splice or single-mode fusion splice has been qualified (QPL'd) for use in pressurized fuselage aircraft or tactical aircraft cable plants. Therefore multimode fiber optic mechanical splices are scored as TRL 6, and single-mode fusion splices are scored as TRL 3.

Optical Fiber

Multimode Fiber

100/140 μm graded index multimode fiber with polyimide buffer coating has been the *defacto* standard for use in tactical aircraft. However, fiber optic cable incorporating this fiber has not been formally QPL'd. Therefore 100/140 μm graded index multimode fiber with polyimide buffer coating is scored as TRL 8.

100/140 μm graded index multimode fiber with acrylate coating has been the *defacto* standard for use in pressurized fuselage aircraft such as the Boeing 777 (as well as seeing widespread application for terrestrial service). Although this specific fiber has not been formally QPL'd for use in aircraft, the flight hour history of this fiber on Boeing 777 aircraft leads one to score high temperature acrylate coated 100/140 μm graded index multimode fiber at TRL 9.

A few other multimode fiber sizes, namely 50/125 μm and 62.5/125 μm have been or are expected to be deployed on tactical aircraft and pressurized fuselage aircraft. These fibers (regardless of coating material) have not been QPL'd in any known cable construction for use in aircraft. However, there are applications where this fiber has proven itself in pressurized fuselage aircraft applications. Therefore a score of TRL 6-7 is given to 50/125 μm and 62.5/125 μm fiber (high temperature acrylate or polyimide coatings).

Single-Mode Fiber

Bend insensitive single-mode fiber and single-mode fiber cable is currently in the development stage for use in tactical aircraft. Core sizes ranging from 4.8 to 9.3 μm have been proposed by the

aerospace research and engineering community. Some candidate single-mode fibers are coated with silicone as opposed to acrylate or polyimide. Novel fiber coatings are also being investigated for aerospace applications. None of the candidate single-mode fiber types have been QPL'd in any specific cable construction. Therefore a score of TRL 4-6 is given to bend insensitive single-mode fiber.

Supportability

Fiber optic maintenance can be subdivided into overarching strategy, troubleshooting, and training [4]. There are two general strategies for maintaining aerospace fiber optic systems – “remove-and-replace” and “repair in place.”

Remove-and-Replace vs. Repair In Place

“Remove-and-replace” requires all links to be designed so that broken parts can be replaced. Examples include feeding fiber optic cables through convoluted tubing and making vulnerable links accessible for replacement. Since this method has been used extensively, its TRL is 8-9.

Unfortunately, in the restricted and crowded space of a tactical aircraft there often is no alternative but to implement a “repair in place” maintenance strategy to repair a broken link. “Repair in place” requires a flight qualified splice, which can survive the full aerospace environment. Since no permanent splice exists, the “repair in place” approach receives a score of TRL 6.

Optical Built-in-Test

Two uni-directional fiber optic links are depicted in Figure 6. Fiber optic transmitter (Tx) devices send optical signals through the aircraft cable plant to fiber optic receiver devices (Rx). Fiber optic connectors on avionics boxes and within the aircraft fuselage connect individual fiber optic cable segments within the airframe. Optical built-in-test technology for on-aircraft detection and isolation of faults in end-to-end fiber optic links does not exist, and little data on optical built-in-test has been reported in the open literature. Therefore optical built-in-test technology readiness is scored as TRL 1.

Figure 6. Two Uni-Directional Fiber Optic Links

Troubleshooting

Fiber optic troubleshooting is well established both commercially and for military/aerospace application. Examples include the commercial fiber optic test procedures (e.g. Telecommunications Industry Association Fiber Optic Test Procedures (TIA FOTPs) [5]) and practices such as the two-jumper method of loss measurement (Figure 7). Consequently, the TRL for troubleshooting is 8.

Figure 7. Example of Loss Measurement

Training

In order to be able to maintain fiber optic equipment on aircraft, an extensive training program is required. Training is critical to both ensure the minimum level of understanding to perform the maintenance correctly as well as to maintain the knowledge between tours of duty. Since military/aerospace fiber optic training programs are not so well developed and still in their relative infancy, the TRL is scored 6.

Support Equipment

Support equipment for maintenance of fiber optic communication links has been thoroughly developed by commercial users. Driven by the telecom market surge up to early 2000, support

equipment tools are mature. Some of this equipment has been modified to satisfy the needs of aircraft maintainers, specifically focused on multimode fiber.

Commercially available support equipment includes optical sources and power meters, the optical time domain reflectometer (OTDR), the visual fault finder, and associated adapter and test lead configurations to connect the troubleshooting tools up to aircraft fiber optic cable plant wiring (Figure 8).

Terminus endface cleaning and inspection tools for on-aircraft maintenance of fiber optic connectors are also commercially available (Figure 9). These tools have been assembled into kits for use in avionics fiber optic maintenance environments. Support equipment is consequently given a score of TRL 7-8.

Figure 8. Example Fiber Optic Link Testing/Troubleshooting Equipment

Figure 9. Example Fiber Optic Inspection and Cleaning Tools

Conclusion for Next Generation Avionics WDM Networks

Next generation avionics fiber optic networks based on WDM technology are still in the very early stage of definition and development. A notional WDM avionics network will likely require tunable or fixed wavelength laser sources, reconfigurable or fixed wavelength add/drop multiplexers/demultiplexers, tunable receivers, gain elements, and single-mode connectors, optical fiber and cable.

Support equipment to troubleshoot WDM links will likely require tunable sources and spectrum analysis equipment to detect and pinpoint cable plant faults containing wavelength dependent components. A single-mode fiber optic splice will likely be needed to repair broken fiber in aircraft fiber optic cable bundles and harnesses. A short reach single-mode OTDR will likely be needed to isolate faults in single-mode fiber cable. Built-in-test technology will be needed to detect and isolate faults in end-to-end transmitter to receiver fiber optic links.

The authors' early technology readiness assessment of notional WDM aerospace network components and supportability are listed in Table 1.

**Table 1. MIL/AERO WDM
Component/Supportability TRLs**

Component	TRL
Tunable / Fixed Wavelength Laser	4
Tunable Receiver	3
Reconfigurable / Fixed Wavelength Add/Drop	1
Integrated Gain Element	2
Single-mode Fiber	4
Single-mode Cable	4
Single-mode Connector	4
Support Equipment	1
Single-mode Splice	3
Training	1
Optical Built-in-Test	1

The Defense Advanced Research Project Agency (DARPA) has made a substantial investment in WDM technology. This investment includes both the development of components as well as the technology to integrate these components and functions into planar lightwave circuits (PLCs). NAVAIR and the Air Force are now investing in the required systems development and technology maturation for transitioning WDM local area network (LAN) technology to military/aerospace platforms.

The work in front of the aerospace industry to apply WDM optical communication will by no means be easy. Much engineering still needs to be

done as is evidenced by the TRLs of the various system elements. TRL 7 is NAVAIR's targeted TRL for next generation WDM LAN components, networks, and supportability.

Based on the technical success of the commercial communications sector and successful development by DARPA, the probability of success is viewed as quite high. Consequently, both industry and the government will continue to invest in development and integration of WDM LAN technology to deliver reliable, scaleable, reconfigurable and maintainable wideband aircraft onboard communication solutions at an acceptable cost and packaging form factor. As the need for onboard communication bandwidth increases, the question is not "IF" WDM optical communication will happen, but rather one of "WHEN."

References

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